

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC CONTROL IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The article discusses the role of public control. The purpose of this work is the study importance of public control in modern society. Public control is carried out in the forms of public monitoring, public inspection, public examination, in other forms that do not contradict this law, as well as in such forms of interaction between civil society institutions and state bodies and local government bodies.

Key words: social institutions, personal status, structure of society, public control and types of social institutions, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается роль общественного контроля. Целью данной работы является исследование значения общественного контроля в современном обществе. Общественный контроль осуществляется в формах общественного надзора, общественного инспектирования, общественной экспертизы, в иных формах, не противоречащих настоящему закону, а также в таких формах взаимодействия институтов гражданского общества с государственными органами и органами местного самоуправления.

Ключевые слова: социальные институты, статус личности, структура общества, общественный контроль, виды социальных институтов, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Public control is a necessary condition for deepening reforms, changing the thinking of people, especially leaders, and increasing their responsibility.

The strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030", developed based on the results of public discussions in order to create a fair and modern state serving the people, identified such priority tasks as: creating the necessary conditions for public participation in the activities of local councils, broad involvement of civil society institutions and gradual digitalization of their activities, establishing the practice of assessing the activities of heads of state bodies and their deputies based on public opinion, intensified continuation of work to form an unacceptable attitude towards corruption in society.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As a result of public control, the activities of state bodies in the country are objectively studied, their shortcomings are identified, various violations of the law are prevented, public participation in the implementation of laws and their preparation is ensured, broader conditions are created for the prompt solution of various problems in society and the expression of the will of the population, and special attention should be paid to the fact that

public control implies not only control over the quality of the work performed, but also the use of opportunities, as well as participation in their development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In our country, consistent work is underway to implement public control and improve the regulatory framework governing this area. The Decree of the President of May 4, 2018 established the badge "For Contribution to the Development of Civil Society", the Resolution of the President of Uzbekistan of July 4, 2018 "On Measures to Organize the Activities of Public Councils under State Bodies" were of great importance in accelerating work in this area. This resolution establishes the procedure for organizing the main tasks, functions, powers and activities of a public council under state bodies, which mainly provides that a public council is created by a decision of the head of a state body, carries out its work on a voluntary basis and is assumed to conduct its work on a public basis, and is also considered as a permanent consultative and advisory body, whose decisions will be advisory in nature. As Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, "there is no more effective tool for achieving the supremacy of the Constitution and the law than public control." Public control is an important institution of democracy and people's power, it serves to ensure the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens by exercising control over the activities of state bodies.

In recent years, our republic has paid special attention to ensuring the participation of citizens in the management of society and public affairs, creating effective mechanisms for implementing public control over the activities of the executive branch, and further strengthening the functions of public control. In particular, at the initiative of the President of Uzbekistan, a public chamber was created in 2020 in order to further strengthen public control and establish close cooperation between the state and society. It was noted that the public chamber should regularly study the opinion of the population, set specific tasks for government agencies to find their solution. The importance of introducing such influential forms of control as "public hearings", "public monitoring", "public examination", "public initiative" was demonstrated.

Of great importance in strengthening the institution of public control was the adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the effectiveness of public control over ongoing reforms in the socio-economic sphere, as well as the activity of citizens in the implementation of democratic reforms in the country" dated October 4, 2019.

At the same time, as the President notes, "public control should not turn into a "one-way traffic". Government agencies are called upon to fairly and objectively consider critical comments not only against citizens, but also against themselves. Decisions on changing the appearance of our regions, construction and improvement must be discussed with local residents and undergo public examination."

Public control should be carried out primarily in relation to the activities of law enforcement and regulatory agencies, and become a significant element in ensuring the rule of law, protecting and ensuring human rights and freedoms. Therefore, the task is set for the courts and investigative bodies, when making decisions on a particular case, to provide explanations and legal comments in response to collective appeals from citizens. That is, real control in this area should be carried out by the people.

The main thing is that the most important vector of state policy remains the firm determination to prevent any form of pressure on public control, violation of the legal rights of media representatives.

The right of the people to control the activities of officials and state bodies is absolute and indisputable. The situation of lack of control leads to official permissiveness and unprecedented corruption. Public intolerance to these negative phenomena must mature, and only the awareness of the need for democratic control by broad sections of the population will stop abuses, egoism, and the decomposition of society.

Foreign experience shows that public control contributes to the effective functioning of the state apparatus, increases the responsibility of state power, competence and professionalism of officials, ensuring proper enforcement of laws, as well as respect for the rights and freedoms of citizens. At the same time, the state, the competent authorities, with the help of feedback from society, are able to take as a basis constructive proposals of citizens and carry out the necessary reforms in the country, relying on their trust and support. In Uzbekistan, as in other countries of the post-Soviet space, public control is considered as a kind of model that the authorities and civil society should follow.

In countries with developed democracies, other conditions for interaction between the state and civil initiatives form a different practice of implementing public control, which includes a fairly wide range of tools and is based on the principles of transparency of state power and participation of society. Public control arose as a need to take into account public opinion when resolving state issues. At the same time, the phrase "public control" itself is practically not used in the West.

In the USA, for example, the institution of public control over the government began to take shape with the emergence and functioning of civil society organizations. Of the 1.5 million [5] public organizations that exist in the USA today, a special type is represented by "public organizations that exercise control over the actions of the authorities... over the conduct of elections and the fulfillment of election promises, conduct investigations and expose facts of corruption, and also actively act on behalf of national minorities" [6]. In Germany, non-governmental organizations, along with legitimate institutions such as parliament and independent courts, are also a key segment of public control, helping to maintain consensus in society [7].

E.A. Ogneva identifies the following as the main features of public control:

- public control acts as a means of ensuring a balance of interests of various social groups;
- the purpose of public control is to protect human rights by uniting and coordinating the efforts of civil society;
- public control is a guarantor of the implementation of social norms;
- public control extends to various spheres of state activity;
- public control is of a mass nature, based on the broad participation of various segments of society;
- participation in the implementation of public control is voluntary [8].

Uzbekistan is implementing phased reforms aimed at strengthening the organizational and legal foundations of public control. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the responsibility of the state to society. Public control was given constitutional

status thanks to the amendments and additions made to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 16, 2014 [9].

At present, more than forty legal acts provide for the right of civil society institutions to exercise public control in such areas as environmental protection, education, healthcare, social protection of the population, consumer protection, and protection of the socio-economic rights of citizens. Significant practical experience has been accumulated by citizens' self-government bodies, trade unions, the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan, and non-governmental non-profit organizations [10]. At the same time, an analysis of the legal foundations of public control in Uzbekistan shows the need to move to a qualitatively new level - from fragmentary topics to a more general law, that is, it is necessary to unify legislation in this area, as well as adopt a single system-forming and basic law. In addition, the current legal acts of Uzbekistan governing issues of public control do not sufficiently disclose the mechanisms for its implementation.

Legality is the strict observance of laws and corresponding legal acts by all state bodies, officials and other persons. This is one of the elements of democracy and the rule of law.

At the same time, this is the principle of precise and universal observance by all state bodies, officials and citizens of the requirements of the Constitution, laws, and other legal acts.

Therefore, every citizen must be informed about the adopted legislative acts, clearly understand the essence of the documents, especially those concerning human rights, and feel their role in their lives.

And the development of laws must take place under the control of society. Only in this case will the laws really serve to ensure human rights, and every citizen will realize the right and responsibility to independently build their own destiny.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to note that in our republic, state public control has been given constitutional status. In the new Uzbekistan, the participation of citizens in the management of society and state affairs, including the development and improvement of public control over the activities of state bodies, provides ample opportunities for the full formation and strengthening of civil society in our country. The stronger the public control in the country, the more humane, free and fair the state is.

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